

The Effect of Fibre Surface Treatment on the Compressive Strength of CFRP Laminates

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ABSTRACT

Two multidirectional carbon fibre laminates were produced with fibres which had been subjected to one of eight levels of surface treatment. Short stable coupons were tested in a modified Celanese compression jig.

Tests showed that the compressive strength increased with increasing fibre surface treatment up to 10% of the standard level after which there was no further improvement in strength. The recorded strengths were approximately 90% of the tensile strengths. The apparent weakness of laminates is ascribed to small degrees of eccentricities in loading. Failure mechanisms were examined microscopically and their effect on compressive strengths considered.

INTRODUCTION

Weight savings and improved performance, compared to conventional materials, have led to an increasing use of fibre reinforced materials in the Aerospace industry. The majority of applications employ laminates with multidirectional fibres.

While there have been numerous studies of static tensile behaviour of multidirectional laminates (1), there is a paucity of compression data. The apparent lack of compression results may be ascribed to specimen instability. The popular approaches used in testing unidirectional composites involve the use of anti-buckling guides or short stable specimens. The Celanese test coupon and jig has been used on short stable specimens with some success (2).

In compression, the rôle of the resin is to support the fibres against premature buckling. This support is provided through the fibre-matrix interface so that the strength of the interface might be expected to influence the compressive behaviour of the laminate. Experiment on unidirectional composites (3) has shown that the compressive strength is reduced at low levels of fibre surface treatment.

In the present study a modification of the Celanese test method has been used to determine the compressive strength of two multidirectional 0, +/- 45 CFRP laminates in which the fibres had been subjected to levels of surface treatment between 0% and 100% of the standard level. A model to explain the compressive

behaviour of the laminates is discussed.

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

Balanced and symmetrical laminates were laid up from 16 layers of pre-impregnated warp sheet made from carbon fibres in epoxy resin. Two different stacking sequences, designated A and B, were produced with lay-ups:-

$$\begin{array}{ll} \text{A (thick layers)} & [(\pm 45)_2, 0_4]_s \\ \text{B (thin layers)} & [(+45, 0, -45, 0)_2]_s \end{array}$$

Before fabrication, the fibres had been subjected to the following percentage levels of the current standard surface treatment:-

$$0, 1, 2, 5, 10, 25L, 25H, \text{ and } 100.$$

Two laminates were prepared with fibres which had 25% surface treatment. The sheet 25L is made from the same batch of fibres as used in the lower levels of surface treatment while 25H contains fibres from the batch used in the higher level of surface treatment.

Reference made to specific laminates is made using a concatenation of the level of surface treatment and the lay-up letter, e.g. 5A or 25LB. No laminate 1B was produced owing to an error in the lay-up procedure, rather a second laminate 1A was produced and designated 1AA.

The laminates, which measured 0.3 m by 0.25 m, were cured in an autoclave at a temperature of 170°C for approximately one hour and postcured at 190°C for four hours. The cured laminates were C-scanned and stored in a controlled environment (23°C and 65% relative humidity). The nominal thickness of the laminates was 2 mm and the fibre volume fraction 60%.

Twelve coupons, 120 mm by 10 mm, were cut from each laminate and etched aluminium end plates, each 50 mm by 10 mm, were bonded to the coupon and arranged so as to expose a central unsupported specimen area of 10 mm square. Short foil strain gauges were bonded to both faces of at least two coupons from each laminate. These gauges, which were arranged parallel to the loading, 0° fibre, axis, allowed a measurement of the compressive modulus and any strain divergence resulting from bending.

Two coupons were waisted in the width prior to testing. The coupons, from laminates 1A and 5A, had a waist radius of 6.4 mm. Specimens were gripped in a modified Celanese jig (4), placed on the compression platen of a screw driven 100 kN testing machine and loaded through a hemispherical cap at a constant crosshead speed of 0.2 mm/min. Failure loads were recorded for all specimens and load-strain plots were obtained from the instrumented specimens. A number of specimens were unloaded after being stressed at close to failure and examined microscopically for evidence of damage.

RESULTS

Table 1 shows the apparent compressive strengths of the specimens. These strengths were calculated by dividing the failure load by (a) the measured cross-sectional areas, and (b) the constant nominal thickness of 2 mm. The latter procedure adjusts strengths to the same volume fraction of fibres. Some of the batches contained one or two specimens with strengths that were markedly lower than the batch mean. These "rogue" values were associated with failures outside the gauge length and/or poor end-plate adhesion. A column of Table 1 contains mean compressive strengths based on samples without these rogue results. The variation of these filtered and corrected values of compressive strength with fibre surface treatment is shown in Fig. 1 for both lay-ups. For less than 10% surface treatment there is a marked reduction in strength. The dispersed lay-up B has a greater compressive strength than the stratified lay-up A. The waisted specimens gave strengths which were similar to those of the parallel-sided coupons.

TABLE 1: Mean Compressive Strengths and Young's Moduli of
(0°, ±45°) CFRP Laminates containing 50% 0° Fibres

Laminate Number	Surface Treatment %	Mean Thickness mm	Apparent Compressive Strength MPa †	Filtered & Corrected Strength * MPa	Compressive Young's Modulus † GPa
OA	0	2.23	582 ± 21	650 ± 25	73.7
OB	0	2.17	656 ± 57	715 ± 60	-
1A	1	2.25	567 ± 47	650 ± 34	74.6
1AA	1	2.23	531 ± 56	620 ± 36	-
2A	2	2.11	696 ± 35	735 ± 35	69.2
2B	2	2.13	793 ± 46	845 ± 50	67.3
5A	5	2.15	751 ± 49	805 ± 55	70.4
5B	5	2.16	822 ± 88	920 ± 35	67.8
10A	10	2.14	821 ± 72	895 ± 55	68.3
10B	10	2.11	820 ± 99	925 ± 47	68.1
25LA	25	2.18	763 ± 57	850 ± 54	67.0
25LB	25	2.19	869 ± 52	950 ± 55	71.7
25HA	25	2.19	780 ± 61	869 ± 29	64.4
25HB	25	2.21	827 ± 36	910 ± 38	65.9
100A	100	2.31	776 ± 52	920 ± 39	70.5
100B	100	2.32	801 ± 70	930 ± 80	71.7
1A**	1	waisted	569	-	-
5A**	5	waisted	858	-	-

* Coupons failing outside the gauge length have been rejected from these figures and values have been corrected to a laminate thickness of 2 mm.

** One value only. Strength quoted for net section.

† Values corrected to a laminate thickness 2 mm.

‡ Means of 12 values ± one standard deviation.

Note: Lay-up A = $[(\pm 45^\circ)_2, 0^\circ_4]_S$, Lay-up B = $[(+45^\circ, 0^\circ, -45^\circ, 0^\circ)_2]_S$

A typical load versus strain plot for an instrumented specimen (from laminate 5B) is shown in Fig. 2. It may be observed that (a) the coupon stiffness decreases with load, opposite to the usual tensile behaviour (1), and (b) the surface strains diverge, appearing as a difference in slope between the traces. Maximum and minimum compressive surface strains are given in Table 2. The compressive failure stress, calculated for an ideal laminate which is everywhere strained to the maximum compressive surface strain, is plotted as a function of surface treatment in Fig. 3. The compressive Young's moduli were obtained from the slope of a secant drawn from the origin to the mean load at 0.5% strain. The values of modulus are presented in the last column of Table 1. There is little variation of modulus with either lay-up or surface treatment implying that, at strains of less than 0.5%, the fibre/matrix bond was sufficient to load and support the fibres for all fibre surface treatments.

Optical microscopy of coupons loaded close to failure showed (Fig. 4.) that considerable inter- and translaminar cracking occurred in the +/- 45° layers of untreated specimens. No damage was observed in the 0° layers, nor was damage detected in any of the specimens with treated fibres. Sections of typical failed coupons are shown in Fig. 5. The specimen with lay-up A contains extensive cracking in the outer +/- 45° layers and a clean break, at about 60° to the loading direction, across the central 0° layer. Delamination between the 45° and the central 0° layers is extensive. Specimens with lay-up B appeared to fan out at the fracture surface with all plies delaminated. Splitting extended from the fracture surface to the grips and appeared to be greater for laminates with less than 10% surface treatment.

TABLE 2: Surface Strains and Their Implications

Laminate Number	Minimum Compressive Surface Strain %	Maximum Compressive Surface Strain %	Difference in Surface Strain %	Compressive Strain at Failure in 0° ply closest to Surface %	Compressive Failure Stress if whole Laminate strained to max. Surface Strain MPa
OA	.77	1.28	.51	1.15	808
OB*	.67	1.12	.45	1.09	889
1A	.65	1.23	.58	1.09	851
1AA	-	-	-	-	-
2A	1.13	1.54	.41	1.44	845
2B	1.27	1.65	.38	1.63	954
5A	1.21	1.63	.42	1.53	923
5B	1.43	1.81	.38	1.79	1028
10A	-	-	-	-	-
10B*	1.91	1.46	.55	1.43	1136
25LA*	.72	1.55	.83	1.34	1156
25LB*	1.48	1.66	.18	1.65	1007
25HA*	1.18	1.80	.62	1.65	1049
25HB*	1.36	1.85	.49	1.82	1047
100A*	.96	1.80	.84	1.59	1199
100B*	1.23	1.82	.59	1.78	1106

* Data from only one test.

DISCUSSION

The divergence of strains observed on opposite faces of the instrumented coupons suggests the presence of an out-of-plane couple resulting from an off-axis loading eccentricity. Strains on the faces are then the combination of the nominal compressive strain ϵ_c and a bending strain $\pm \epsilon_b$. From a knowledge of the surface strains it is possible to estimate the eccentricity of loading using simple bending theory (5). The mean eccentricity was 0.07 mm with a standard deviation of 0.03 mm. It may also be shown that the ratio of failure stresses of laminates B and A should be about 1.05 if the mean eccentricity is taken and failure is assumed to occur when a critical surface strain is reached. This apparent improvement of the compressive strength of lay-up B with respect to lay-up A is a direct result of the former's higher flexural stiffness. The ratio of the flexural stiffnesses of B and A is very nearly 2. Thus the occurrence of eccentric loading could explain both the scatter in the recorded compressive strengths for a given laminate and the higher strength shown by lay-up B. If the critical strain were the same in tension and compression, the eccentric loading model would suggest that the recorded mean compressive strength of lay-up A should be about 90% of the tensile strength while lay-up B should develop compressive strengths of about 95% of the tensile strength. For surface treatments above 10% the compressive strength levels attained were within 10% of the mean tensile strengths (6,7) and more than one third greater than compression strengths reported for similar multidirectional materials (7,8).

The stress developed in the 0° fibres (for treated specimens) was about 1.6 GPa while most compressive strengths reported for unidirectional material lie in the range 1.0 to 1.4 GPa (9). The difference may be accounted for partly by support of the 0° fibres from the 45° layers and partly due to the fact that larger specimens were used in the unidirectional tests so that premature macro-buckling may have occurred. Work on very short coupons (less than 4 mm) has produced compressive strengths in excess of 1.8 GPa (7,9,10). If the bending strains are included, the stresses in the 0° fibres closest to the face of the

coupon could be in excess of 1.9 GPa which is similar to or greater than the tensile strength of unidirectional material (1).

It has been suggested, above, that coupon failure might occur when a critical value of surface strain is reached. In the presence of axial and bending loads it would be expected that the nominal applied load and strain would be less than this critical value. The evidence presented in Table 2 suggests that the critical surface strain depends upon fibre surface treatment and, possibly, lay-up. These results are, however, based on a small number of instrumented specimens. It may be that other failure mechanisms may be called into play as the experimental parameters are changed. Another failure criteria could be that of a critical strain in the 0° fibres nearest the surface. Such strains are recorded in Table 2. These strains are much greater in the dispersed lay-up B but, as with the critical surface strain, the evidence is insufficient to claim that these are unique. Equally, a failure criterion based on critical strains developed in the 45° layers might be invoked. Whatever the failure hypothesis adopted, it is apparent that failure will be initiated in either the 0° or 45° layers closest to the surface.

With the available experimental evidence it is difficult to establish a failure mechanism. Compressive tests which were interrupted just before the expected failure load, provided specimens which could be sectioned and inspected for damage. There was no visible damage in specimens with more than 5% fibre surface treatment even when pre-loaded to 97% of the expected failure load. Untreated specimens showed extensive inter- and translamellar cracking in the 45° layers but there was no damage apparent in the 0° layers.

Two possible failure mechanisms are discussed in a fuller report (4).

CONCLUSIONS

A modified Celanese jig has been used to determine the compression strength of two multidirectional CFRP lay-ups. Measured compressive strengths increased rapidly with fibre surface treatment until about 10% of the current standard level after which a plateau was reached. These compressive strengths were within about 10% of the tensile strengths and, if stresses are calculated on the basis of the measured maximum surface strains, these tensile strengths may be exceeded. The multidirectional lay-up B which had thin, dispersed, layers was stronger than that which had thick layers - lay-up A. If eccentric loading can be eliminated, lay-ups A and B could attain the same compressive strength for a given surface treatment and this may be greater than the tensile strength.

REFERENCES

- 1 Curtis, P.T. "The Effect of Edge Stresses on the Failure of (0° , 45° , 90°) CFRP Laminates", RAE (Royal Aircraft Establishment, Farnborough, UK) TR 80054, 1980.
- 2 ASTM D3410 - 75, July 1979.
- 3 Dunford, D.V., Harvey, J., Hutchings, J. and Judge, C. "The Effect of Surface Treatment of Type 2 Carbon Fibre on CFRP Properties", RAE TR 81096, 1981.
- 4 Curtis, P.T. and Morton, J. "The Effect of Fibre Surface Treatment on the Compressive Strength of CFRP Laminates", RAE Tech. Report in press.
- 5 Timoshenko, S.P. Strength of Materials, Van Nostrand, Pt I, 1962, p 249.
- 6 Curtis, P.T. and Dorey, G. "Hole Interactions in CFRP and Aluminium Alloys", RAE TR 79138, 1979.
- 7 Curtis, P.T. Unpublished work, RAE Materials Department (1980-81).
- 8 Rhodes, F.E. Private communication, British Aerospace, Weybridge, UK.
- 9 Woolstencroft, D.H., Curtis, A.R. and Haresceugh, R.I. "Comparison of Test Techniques used for the Evaluation of the Unidirectional Compressive Strength of Carbon Fibre Reinforced Plastic", Composites, Vol 12, 1981, pp 275-280.
- 10 Woolstencroft, D.H. Private communication, British Aerospace, Preston,

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Fig. 1. Plot of compressive strength versus % surface treatment for (0, +/-45) CFRP laminates containing 50% 0° fibres. (○ = lay-up A, and ● = lay-up B)

Fig. 2. Typical plot of strain versus applied load for a CFRP coupon with strain gauges on both surfaces (laminate 5B).

Fig. 3. Maximum calculated surface stress versus fibre surface treatment. (○ = lay-up A, and ● = lay-up B)

(magn. × 160)

Fig. 4. Cracking (arrowed) in the outer 45° plies of a lay-up A coupon, with untreated carbon fibres, loaded close to the mean failure stress and unloaded.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 5. Failed coupons from (a) lay-up A (2LA), and (b) lay-up B (25LB). Note 45° layers appear dark. (magn. $\times 14$)